

Case Studies in Bioeconomy education, training and skills development

Case study sample: Design in
Education and Education Design

Estonia

CIVITTA

Design in Education and Education Design

1 Abstract

The microdegree focuses on learning through practical participation and teaching. The programme aims to teach educators how to integrate different learning subjects, facilitate creativity, and adopt a problem-centred approach. It emphasises keeping learning engaging and appropriate to the learners' needs while incorporating and covering various design fields (e.g., product design, applied arts). One of the outcomes of this microdegree is the development of skills to create novel educational approaches.

2 Target Groups

Current and future teachers (both in basic education and recreational education) of all educational subjects; Education providers with a Bachelor's degree

3 Case Study Category

Art to elicit new ways of thinking and develop skills needed in bioeconomy education

4 Training Provider

Estonian Academy of Arts

5 Region

Tallinn, Estonia

6 Language

Estonian, English

7 Objectives of the education Format

Complementing education for professionals

8 Final objective of the education format

The objective of the curriculum is to:

1. Develop skills for education design and ability to incorporate design into education.
2. Apply design thinking, design processes, creativity, and problem-solving skills to education.
3. Apply co-creation, person-centered thinking; slow design and sustainability; visual, creative and design thinking; identity and meaningful creation as the basis and concepts of modern design in education.
4. Promote seeing the world from different perspectives.

9 Scope and context of the education format

This curriculum has six modules:

1. Design fundamentals
2. Education design
3. Product design
4. Graphic design
5. Fashion, accessory and textile design
6. Applied art

Microdegree lasts for 416 academic hours.

10 Specific Skills and competencies addressed

Students who complete the microdegree programme will:

- Have knowledge of the principles of teaching contemporary design and applied art, as well as the main principles and concepts of design.
- Be able to analyse and apply an innovative academic approach based on design philosophy.
- Be able to apply a creative approach and a sustainable and inclusive mindset in integrating subjects.
- Be able to create a learning environment based on design philosophy and a learning journey that considers user experience.
- Use design methodology in academic work and in preparing and providing feedback on creative assignments.

11 European Qualification Framework levels/s

Level 5

Level 6

12 Main benefit of the participant

Certificate of completion of the continuing education of the Academy of Arts or a certificate of hours completed if at least half of the curriculum has been passed.

13 Investment made

The current (as of January 2024) price of the microdegree is 1,520 euros.

14 Importance and impact

This curriculum has only been taught since the 2023/24 academic year.

15 Relevance (of the format)

Considering BioGov's objective of finding novel education models, the skills of education design, which also incorporate arts and design—another objective of BioGov—make this curriculum very relevant.

16 Uniqueness and replicability in BioGov.net

This is a unique curriculum in the Estonian context as it encompasses a wide variety of different design fields and also includes the design of education. The Estonian Academy of Arts does not have a curriculum specifically dedicated to teaching teachers, which allows it to offer a unique perspective on novel teaching methods.

One of the main objectives of BioGov is to identify case studies for novel training frameworks; a curriculum containing the design of education can offer a new perspective on different training methods.

17 Data sources

- **Online resources:** <https://www.artun.ee/avatud-akadeemia/disain-hariduses-ja-haridusdisain/>
- **Resource persons:**
- **Other sources, if any:**

BioGov.net

Governance & Upskilling for a
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